

BLAST RESPONSE OF PANELS CONTAINING SUSTAINABLE MATERIALSChris J. von Klemperer¹, Genevieve S. Langdon², Sherlyn Gabriel³, Steeve Chung Kim Yuen⁴¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Cape Town, South Africa,
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of Cape Town, South Africa, steeve.chungkimyuen@uct.ac.za**Keywords:** Natural Fibre Composites, Sustainability, Blast Loading**ABSTRACT**

Manufacturing fibre reinforced polymer composites from sustainable materials can be achieved by using natural fibres such as Flax and Jute and binding them with a bio-oil based epoxy such as Entropy Resin's SuperSap CLR. These materials are often utilised in transportation applications where they provide the light weight required, and help the manufacturer meet the sustainable requirements of regulations and market pressures.

While there has been a lot of research into the quasi-static strength of these materials and some research into the impact properties, there is very little on the response of these materials to air blast. From a design perspective it is important to understand the level of protection which can be expected from these materials.

This work compares the response of fibre glass reinforced epoxy laminates, to Jute and Flax reinforced epoxy laminates. The natural fibre reinforced composites performed badly providing very limited protection as they tended to fail in a brittle manner when exposed to the detonation of very low charge masses of PE4 explosive. Interestingly the Jute fibre based composites were particularly bad and panels ruptured at the lowest charge masses tested. Comparing a standard marine grade epoxy and a bio-oil based epoxy resin in flax fibre reinforced composites revealed that the sustainable resin had minimal if any measurable effect on the response and level of protection.

1 INTRODUCTION

Environmental impact and sustainability are increasingly important factors in engineering design and materials selection. Traditional Fibre Reinforced Polymeric (FRP) composites such as Glass Fibre reinforced Epoxy have tended to be based on non-renewable resources. This is especially true for the polymeric resins which are usually fossil fuel based. Furthermore, these traditional FRPs are difficult to recycle. This is particularly unfortunate since FRPs are used in high strength / low weight applications, for example in transportation, where they can be used to save mass and improve performance. This has resulted in a significant research and industrial impetus to develop "sustainable" composites. The definition of exactly what is sustainable varies, but two common approaches are, however, the use of a natural fibre reinforcement material (rather than the usual glass or carbon fibres) and the use of resins formulated with renewable resources such as plant oils.

Joshi et al [1] have shown that Natural Fibre Reinforced Polymer (NFRP) composites can be considered to be environmentally compatible and thus sustainable because of the lower energy requirement to manufacture and to dispose of the resulting composite. Natural fibres also tend to have a lower density than glass fibres resulting in a mass saving. However, compared to glass or carbon fibres, the relatively poor strength properties of the natural fibres can result in a weak composite. Consequently, the use of NFRPs has been restricted to non-structural applications.

Entropy Resins[2] claim a 33% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions resulting from the production of their SuperSap epoxy resins. These SuperSap resins include a mixture of plant based bio oils as well as co-products and waste products from other industrial processes; resulting in a reported bio-based carbon content of between 21 and 29%. This resin formulation is often used as an example of a sustainable or green matrix for FRP composites in research publications [3, 4]. Currently these types of sustainable composites containing natural fibres and bio-based epoxy resins are already used in automotive, marine and mass transportation industries. [5-8].

The response of NFRPs to quasi-static and impact loading has been reported in literature[9-11], but there is almost no reported data on the response of these materials to blast loading. Terror attacks as well as accidental explosions pose a risk to occupants in transportation vehicles. An understanding of the response of these sustainable composites to blast loading is crucial for design purposes. There is a reasonable amount of data on the response of traditional FRP composites to blast loading, [12, 13] but very few studies on NFRPs exposed to blast loading or the impact of bio-based epoxy resins. This paper presents some preliminary results of work into this topic and compares the results to the response of blast loading on a standard glass fibre / epoxy laminate.

2 MATERIALS, MANUFACTURING AND PROPERTIES

A control material of a plain weave E-glass (400 g/m²) and a Gurit marine grade epoxy resin (Prime 20 LV) was initially selected. For relevance and usefulness, a standard industrial manufacturing process (VARTM) was selected as the manufacturing method for the test specimens. In all cases, large flat panels were manufactured in a single shot process with the test specimens for quasi-static testing and blast loading all cut from these large panels. The response of this control material has been previously reported on in reference [12] and thus provides a useful performance baseline.

The natural fibres tested were a flax fabric (550 g/m² 2x2 twill weave) and a Biotex Jute fabric (400 g/m² 2 x 2 twill weave). The second resin system utilised was a SuperSap CLR epoxy resin from Entropy Resins. [2].

Table 1 shows the various combinations of resins and reinforcement and the number of layers of fibre used to obtain similar mass specimens. The various composites manufactured had a similar areal density to allow for simple comparison of the results and ensure that the mass of the panel did not affect the blast response. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the VARTM manufacturing process used, and Figure 2 shows a photograph of a natural fibre reinforced composite panel at the end of this infusion process. In all cases the panels were post cured according to the resin specifications prior to cutting on a saw or CNC Router.

Reinforcement Material	Resin system	Lay up (All VARTM)	Average mass (kg) / thickness (mm) of 300 x 300 mm blast test panel
<i>Glass Fibre (Control)</i>	<i>Prime 20 LV Epoxy</i>	<i>19 layers, 400 g/m² plain weave, all 0/90</i>	<i>1.00 / 6.20</i>
<i>Flax fabric</i>	<i>Prime 20 LV Epoxy</i>	<i>9 layers, 550 g/m² 2x2 twill weave, all 0/90</i>	<i>1.09 / 9.81</i>
<i>Flax Fabric</i>	<i>Super Sap CLR Epoxy</i>	<i>9 layers, 550 g/m² 2x2 twill weave, all 0/90</i>	<i>1.09 / 9.93</i>
<i>Biotex Jute fabric</i>	<i>Prime 20 LV Epoxy</i>	<i>13 layers, 400 g/m² 2x2 twill weave, all 0/90</i>	<i>1.03 / 9.91</i>

Table 1: Manufacturing matrix showing the various types of specimens.

The specimens were subjected to quasi-static flexural tests with the dual aim of validating the repeatability and consistency of the manufactured panels as well as providing basic information regarding the strength of the material. Table 2 shows the average results from the quasi-static tests. As

expected, the NFRPs exhibited lower flexural strength and chord of elasticity than the control glass fibre reinforced composites, with the flax reinforced SuperSap performing the worst. Figure 3 shows examples of stress vs strain for the Flax / Prime 20 and Jute / Prime 20.

Figure 1: Schematic of VARTM manufacturing process.

Figure 2: Photograph of an infused natural fibre composite panel.

	Maximum flexural stress		Flexural chord of elasticity.		Flexural strain at failure.	
	Mean (MPa)	Std Dev (MPa)	Mean (GPa)	Std Dev (MPa)	Mean (m/m)	Std Dev (m/m)
<i>Glass Fibre Prime 20 LV Epoxy</i>	465.4	25.40	21.60	766	0.029	0.001
<i>Flax fabric Prime 20 LV Epoxy</i>	111.8	5.99	6.25	479	0.030	0.002
<i>Flax Fabric Super Sap CLR Epoxy</i>	76.6	5.56	3.86	462	0.044	0.007
<i>Biotex Jute fabric Prime 20 LV Epoxy</i>	88.9	8.99	6.20	809	0.019	0.001

Table 2: Results of flexural tests.

Figure 3: Stress vs Strain curves obtained from the quasi-static flexural tests

3 BLAST TEST METHOD

Using a horizontal ballistic pendulum, as shown in Figure 4, the 300 x 300 mm blast specimens were clamped using bolts between two picture frame clamping plates. A square section (200 x 200 mm which corresponds to the exposed area) blast tube, 200 mm long, was attached to the front clamp. PE4 explosive in Ø30 mm circular disks was detonated at the open end of the tube, as shown in Figure 4. The blast tube ensured that the propagating blast waves provided a near-uniform load on the specimens. The mass of the explosive was varied to obtain a range of responses in the specimens. The range of charge masses and types of panels tested are listed in table 3. The pendulum motion resulting from the blast was measured using a laser displacement sensor. Using simple vibration theory with the known natural frequency and mass of the pendulum, the impulse transferred to the specimen was determined. This set up has been successfully used for a number of years for similar work [13]. A photograph of the ballistic pendulum utilized for this work is shown in Figure 5.

The panels were inspected post blast test to identify the damage caused by the blast. The modes of failure as well as the point of rupture were noted. Measurement of the permanent deformation (where applicable) as well as measurements of visible damage such as delamination area and crack lengths were recorded.

Figure 4: Experimental blast test set up showing the 200 x 200 x 200 mm blast tube and a schematic of the horizontal ballistic pendulum.

Reinforcement	Panel type		Tested charge masses of PE4 (g)
		Resin	
<i>Glass Fibre (Control)</i>		<i>Prime 20 LV Epoxy</i>	5, 7, 11, 11, 25
<i>Flax fabric</i>		<i>Prime 20 LV Epoxy</i>	5, 6, 7, 9, 11
<i>Flax Fabric</i>		<i>Super Sap CLR Epoxy</i>	5, 6, 7, 9, 11
<i>Biotex Jute fabric</i>		<i>Prime 20 LV Epoxy</i>	4, 5, 5, 6, 7

Table 3: Summary of the blast charge masses and the various composite panels tested

Figure 5: Photograph of the BISRU horizontal ballistic pendulum.

4 RESULTS

Figure 6 shows the relationship between the explosive charge mass and the impulse imparted onto the target panel. Overall a reasonably linear relationship between the charge mass and impulse was noted. As with most blast tests, there was some experimental variation in the data. Nevertheless these results fit data from previous tests on flat plates exposed to uniform blast loading.

Figure 6: Graph of Charge mass vs Impulse for the blast tests.

The blast tested panels were all assessed for any measurable permanent deformation. Figure 7 shows the graph of the permanent deformation (at the centre of the panels) vs charge mass for the four different materials tested. Best fit trend lines have been added to indicate the damage progression where possible. It can be noted that the glass fibre / Prime 20 panels had almost no permanent deformation up to 25 g. The NFRP panels were substantially weaker and all suffered damage resulting in an exponentially increasing permanent deformation. The Jute reinforced panels were noticeably more damaged than the Flax. There was very little measurable difference in the two resin systems (Prime 20 and Super Sap CLR) when considering the flax reinforced panels. The nature of composite materials means that it is unusual to see plastic deformation in the way that a metal such as steel will deform. This applied to the glass fibre panels tested in this work. The natural fibre reinforced panels did not, however, follow this trend. Substantial damage resulted in significant permanent deformation to the NFRP panels was observed.

Figure 7: Graph of Charge mass vs permanent centre point deflection for the blast tests.

In terms of failure modes, the glass fibre / Prime 20 (control) panels exhibited visible delamination and some fibre breakage in the range tested. The delamination damage was not observed until the charge mass reached 25 g. This delamination damage can be observed in Figure 8(a). Delamination was observed in the glass fibre panel as a shadow starting at the midpoint of the 4 sides and expanding into the panel. The lower charge mass tests produced very little visible damage in the panels with just some minor fibre breakage along the clamp frame edge. This was most likely due to a stamping / shearing effect of the back face on the edge of the clamp frame.

The NFRP panels behaved very differently with substantial cracks and fracture occurring as shown in Figures 8(b) and 8(c) for the Jute / Prime 20 and Flax / Prime 20 respectively. Both natural fibre specimens had extensive through-thickness cracking. The Jute panel shattered into pieces. Figure 8(b) was taken after the panel was reassembled as in a jigsaw puzzle. The flax reinforced panel out-performed the Jute reinforced panel at the 11 g charge mass, but still exhibited extensive through-thickness cracking with the onset of complete rupture and failure of the panel. The behaviour of the Jute and Flax reinforced materials was very brittle in nature.

Figure 8: Photographs of the back faces of the tested panels.

Upon examination after sectioning the panels post blast, no obvious delamination within the material was observed suggesting that the resin strength properties dominated the fibre properties. This was opposite of what was observed in the glass fibre / epoxy materials. While the flax panel showed some damage initiation along the clamp frame edge as noted in the glass fibre panels, it was not as severe as the Jute panel which had disintegrated with shearing occurring along the clamp frame boundary.

Figure 9 shows photographs of the back faces of various panels made from the three different materials subjected to a 6 g charge mass. The Jute (Figure 9(a)) was clearly the worst performing with significant cracks visible all over the back face. The Flax / Prime 20 (Figure 9(b)) and Flax / SuperSap (Figure 9(c)) had significantly less damage with some cracks visible extending from the centre of the panel. For comparison a glass fibre / Prime 20 panel exposed to 7 g of explosive, shown in Figure 10, showed no visible damage. The black markings on the panel in the clamp frame region were the result of DIC speckle paint which was applied to the back face of the panel. This paint was removed from the exposed area post blast testing for inspection.

(a) Jute/Prime 20 panel (b) Flax /Prime 20 panel (c) Flax/SuperSap
 Figure 9: Photographs of the back faces of different panels subjected to 6 g of explosive.

Figure 10: Photograph of the back face of a glass fibre /Prime 20 panel exposed to 7 g

An attempt was made to quantify the damage in the NFRP panels by measuring the total through thickness crack length. This was performed by an image analysis tool using MATLAB. Figure 11 details this process on the back face of a Jute /Prime 20 specimen exposed to a 6 g charge mass. Once the image has been processed to identify the through thickness cracks (shown in red), the total length of these cracks can be measured. The lengths of crack measured from the back face vs the charge mass are plotted in Figure 12 for the Flax and Jute reinforced composites. The process was performed on the front and back faces of the blast tested specimens. The explosive residue on the front face, did affect this process somewhat and made the data from the back faces more useful.

Figure 11: A series of images showing the image processing steps performed to measure the total through thickness crack length on the back face of a Jute / Prime 20 panel exposed to 6g of PE4.

For all three sustainable materials, a near linear relation was noted for the increase in crack length (and hence damage) as the charge mass was increased. Linear trend lines have been added to the graph in Figure 12. The results further confirmed that the Jute reinforced material was significantly worse than the Flax based materials. The Jute reinforced Prime 20 had a very steep gradient compared to the other materials demonstrating a quick rise in the crack lengths. As noted for the permanent deformation results, there was very little difference between the two resin systems when used with Flax. The Prime 20 reinforced Flax panels had slightly more cracking than the SuperSap, but the results were not significantly different.

Figure 12: A series of images showing the image processing steps performed to measure the total through thickness crack length on the back face of a Jute / Prime 20 panel exposed to 6g of PE4.

An attempt was made to identify the failure mode progression for the tested materials. Table 4 shows the basic damage progression and an approximate initiation point of that damage. The following modes of failure were identified and noted.

- FC - Fibre failure and Cracking (Through thickness cracking of the panel and failure of individual fibres within the panel)
- DL - Delamination (Failure of the bond between the layers making up the composite panels)
- BF - Boundary Failure (Failure at the boundary, caused by fibre and/or matrix failure and / or shearing against the clamp frame edge)
- RF - Rupture and / or Fragmentation of the panel resulting in a hole(s).

Panel type		Charge masses of PE4 (g)						
Reinforcement	Resin	4	5	6	7	9	11	25
<i>Glass Fibre</i>	<i>Prime 20 LV Epoxy</i>	-	None	-	None	-	BF*	BF, DL*
<i>Flax fabric</i>	<i>Prime 20 LV Epoxy</i>	-	FC*	FC, BF*	FC, BF	FC, BF	FC, BF	-
<i>Flax Fabric</i>	<i>Super Sap CLR Epoxy</i>	-	FC*	FC	FC	FC, BF*	FC, BF	-
<i>Biotex Jute fabric</i>	<i>Prime 20 LV Epoxy</i>	None	FC*, BF*, RF*	FC, BF	FC, BF, RF	-	FC, BF, RF	-

Table 4: Failure modes identified in the various panels. Note a * indicates initiation of a mode for that material.

The glass fibre panel experienced only two modes of failure within the tested charge mass range, with some damage along the boundary edge most likely due to shearing against the clamp frame, and delamination initiating at charge masses between 11 and 25 g. The NFRP panels were all weaker with through-thickness cracks appearing from charge masses as low as 5 g. This is about the minimum charge mass which could be reliably detonated with the experimental set up. The boundary shearing appeared to follow the initial through thickness cracking. For the Flax reinforced composites, it was noted that the boundary shearing started later in the SuperSap resin panels compared to the Prime 20 panels. The Jute was the worst performing with complete rupture initiating at a charge mass as low as 5 g. The rupture initiation point is important as it gives a simple indication of the level of protection. Rupture and pieces flying off the panel results in fragments which will cause more damage or injuries if these panels are used to provide protection. The Jute was also inconsistent in its response with the 6 g charge not causing rupture.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A series of sustainable composite panels using natural fibres as the reinforcement as well as traditional epoxy and a bio-based epoxy resin were constructed and tested. Glass fibre / epoxy panels were also tested to provide a baseline. Considering equivalent areal density, the glass fibre was significantly better when exposed to uniform blast tests. The glass fibre panels survived blast loading of up to 25 g of PE4 detonated 200 mm away with only minor delamination. In comparison the Jute fibre reinforced epoxy specimens ruptured effectively providing no protection of any sort, at a charge mass of 5 g. The Flax reinforced specimens exhibited significant through thickness cracking, again starting from a charge mass as low as 5 g.

It was clear from these tests that Flax fabric makes a better composite than the Jute. This was borne out by all the blast test analyses and results but was not what was expected based on the quasi-static tests reported in table 2. The large variation and scatter in the data on the Jute reinforced material tests further reduces its suitability as a structural or blast protective material.

The response and failure mechanisms of the natural fibre panels was very different to those usually observed in traditional FRP composites. In many cases the response was very brittle in nature and the lack of delamination tends to suggest that the fibre was not providing much reinforcement, rather the resin properties are dominating the strength of the composite.

Unfortunately, this work showed that glass fibre remains the reinforcement material of choice for blast protection. In cases where natural fibre composites are potentially exposed to blast, a hybrid of glass fibre and natural fibre may be the best solution to ensure reasonable levels of protection. A positive from a sustainability perspective, however, was that the bio-oil based SuperSap appears to be as effective as the traditional Prime 20 epoxy when used as a matrix for flax reinforced composites.

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